

SURE
SUSTAINABLE
RESILIENT
EU FARMING
SYSTEMS **Farm**

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T4.2: Assessing how policies enable or constrain the resilience of a small-scale perennial crop system (hazelnuts) in Tuscia, Central Italy.

An application of the Resilience Assessment Tool (ResAT)

Work Performed by P10, Università degli Studi della Tuscia, Italy (UNITUS)

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1. Introduction

Italy is the second largest world producer of hazelnut after Turkey. Around 1/3 of the Italian production comes from Lazio region, where this crop generates 73 Million of Euro of added value (2015) (INEA). Here there are more than 6000 hazelnut farms for around 19000 ha, 94% of which are located in the case study area of Viterbo. The quality of the product is high in comparison with the international competitors.

The main area of hazelnut production in Lazio is Monti Cimini around the Vico lake. It is characterized by a strong vocation especially in the most central zone. Here more than 80% of the farms produce hazelnut that uses more than 55% of the whole UAA (ISTAT 2015)

The main challenges and risk for this farming system may be classified in the following four categories.

- a) Socio-demographic: more than 50% of hazelnut farms are managed by farmers over 65 years. High age of farmers and constraints to generational turnover obstruct entrepreneurship, innovation and investment in this farming systems.
- b) Political factors: unstable political situation in Turkey, whose production is more than 60% of the world production and where domestic policy supports heavily this sector, may cause high and unpredictable volatility in the market.
- c) Consumers preferences: Increasing sanitary concerns regarding fat rich processed food with high content of hazelnuts, such as Nutella.
- d) Market instability: Price volatility occurred in recent years together with high fixed cost require for planting such a perennial crop might prevent investment and affect economic and financial sustainability. Furthermore, downstream concentration in the supply chain (Ferrero is by large the main buyer) makes the farming system heavily dependent on downstream buyers' strategies.
- e) Environmental factors: Hazelnut crops are high water demanding mostly in the hottest months; increasing water scarcity and weather temperature due to climate change put significant pressure on quality and yields. Furthermore, possible diffusion of new bugs such as *Halyomorpha halys* might be highly detrimental for product quality.

2. Data collection

2.1 – Criteria for policy documents collection

To select the relevant policy documents according our case study we went through the following steps:

- meetings with several stakeholders that allowed us to identify the main policies affecting the case study region.
- selection of documents establishing, regulating and implementing such policies at different levels of government (European Union, member State, regional government (Lazio)).
- classification of the documents according to the main policies previously identified.

In the first step we have identified two main policies:

- a) the policies established within the single Common Market Organization (CMO - first pillar of CAP) aimed at supporting Producers Organizations (POs) and their activities for better horizontal and vertical coordination in the value chain; such policies are regulated at national level through the National Strategy plan and implemented through the Operational Plans formulated by the POs
- b) the Rural Development Policies (RDP - second pillar of CAP) whose broad-spectrum provisions, supporting structural re-organization of economic activities in rural areas, may affect substantially the farmers' strategies to face with changes of the economic and environmental context. Such policies are regulated by the National Rural Development Programme and the Rural Development Plan approved by the regional government (Lazio).

Finally, the assessment has been based only on official policy documents. This is to carry out a rigorous and not second-hand analysis.

2.2 - List of policy documents selected

2.2.1 - Common Market Organization (CMO)

Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 establishing a common organisation of the markets in agricultural products and repealing Council Regulations (EEC) No 922/72, (EEC) No 234/79, (EC) No 1037/2001 and (EC) No 1234/2007
Regolamento (UE) n. 1308/2013 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio, del 17 dicembre 2013 , recante organizzazione comune dei mercati dei prodotti agricoli e che abroga i regolamenti (CEE) n. 922/72, (CEE) n. 234/79, (CE) n. 1037/2001 e (CE) n. 1234/2007 del Consiglio (varie lingue)
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/it/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32013R1308>

Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2017/891 of 13 March 2017 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the fruit and vegetables and processed fruit and vegetables sectors and supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1306/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to penalties to be applied in those sectors and amending Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 543/2011

Regolamento delegato (UE) 2017/891 della Commissione, del 13 marzo 2017, che integra il regolamento (UE) n. 1308/2013 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio per quanto riguarda i settori degli ortofrutticoli e degli ortofrutticoli trasformati, integra il regolamento (UE) n. 1306/2013 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio per quanto riguarda le sanzioni da applicare in tali settori e modifica il regolamento di esecuzione (UE) n. 543/2011 della Commissione (varie lingue)

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/IT/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32017R0891>

Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/892 of 13 March 2017 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the fruit and vegetables and processed fruit and vegetables sectors

Regolamento di esecuzione (UE) 2017/892 della Commissione, del 13 marzo 2017, recante modalità di applicazione del regolamento (UE) n. 1308/2013 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio per quanto riguarda i settori degli ortofrutticoli e degli ortofrutticoli trasformati (varie lingue)

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/IT/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32017R0892>

DM n. 5460 del 3 agosto 2011 "Aggiornamento della Strategia Nazionale 2009-2013 e della Disciplina ambientale nazionale, in materia di organizzazioni di produttori ortofrutticoli, di fondi di esercizio e di programmi operativi, adottata con Decreto ministeriale 25 settembre 2008 n. 3417"

<https://www.politicheagricole.it/flex/cm/pages/ServeBLOB.php/L/IT/IDPagina/4071>

DM n. 4969 del 29 agosto 2017 "Strategia nazionale in materia di riconoscimento e controllo delle organizzazioni di produttori ortofrutticoli e loro associazioni, di fondi di esercizio e di programmi operativi, per il periodo 2018-2022"

<https://www.politicheagricole.it/flex/cm/pages/ServeBLOB.php/L/IT/IDPagina/11602>

DM n. 5927 del 18 ottobre 2017 - "Disposizioni nazionali in materia di riconoscimento e controllo delle organizzazioni di produttori ortofrutticoli e loro associazioni, di fondi di esercizio e di programmi operativi" - Pubblicato in GURI n. 31 del 7 febbraio 2018

<https://www.politicheagricole.it/flex/cm/pages/ServeBLOB.php/L/IT/IDPagina/11803>

2.2.2 – Rural Development Policy (RDP)

Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1698/2005

Regolamento (UE) n. 1305/2013 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio, del 17 dicembre 2013, sul sostegno allo sviluppo rurale da parte del Fondo europeo agricolo per lo sviluppo rurale (FEASR) e che abroga il regolamento (CE) n. 1698/2005 del Consiglio (varie lingue)

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/IT/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32013R1305>

Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 807/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and introducing transitional provisions

Regolamento delegato (UE) n. 807/2014 della Commissione, dell' 11 marzo 2014 , che integra talune disposizioni del regolamento (UE) n. 1305/2013 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio sul sostegno allo sviluppo rurale da parte del Fondo europeo agricolo per lo sviluppo rurale (FEASR) e che introduce disposizioni transitorie (varie lingue)

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/IT/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0807>

Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 808/2014 of 17 July 2014 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) Regolamento di esecuzione (UE) n. 808/2014 della Commissione, del 17 luglio 2014 , recante modalità di applicazione del regolamento (UE) n. 1305/2013 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio sul sostegno allo sviluppo rurale da parte del Fondo europeo agricolo per lo sviluppo rurale (FEASR) (varie lingue)

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/IT/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0808>

FEASR 2014-2020 - National Rural Development Programme - Italy

<https://www.reterurale.it/psrn>

FEASR 2014-2020 - Rural Development Plan (Regional) - Lazio

http://www.lazioeuropa.it/files/140723/regione_lazio_psr_feasr_2014_2020_luglio_2014.pdf

http://lazioeuropa.it/files/180119/programme_2014it06rdp005_5_1_it.pdf

3. Analysis

3.1 – Interpretation and scoring of the data

The analysis of the policy documents has been carried out separately for the two main policies identified: Common Market Organization and Rural Development Policy. The overview of the policies' features associated to the to each type and characteristics of resilience is presented in the table A.1 in the annex.

Following the analysis, two agricultural economists and one agronomist, with a consolidated experience on the case study region, have interpreted and scored the results of the analysis. The consolidated results are reported in the following table.

Table 1: Likert scale of the policy goals and instruments

Question	Scale (0-5)	Arguments
<i>ROBUSTNESS</i>		
1a. To what extent is a focus on the short-term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	2	Both CMO and RDP objectives refer to medium and long term adjustments
1b. To what extent is a focus on the short- term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	3	Some RDP measures (such as natural disasters, catastrophic events and payments to areas facing natural or other specific constraints) are focused on short term adjustments.
2a. To what extent is protection of the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	3	Amongst the RDP objectives, a not negligible number of the RDP objectives concern refers to restore pre-existing conditions after natural events and maintain activities in particular areas.
2b. To what extent is protection of the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	4	Some RDP measures (such as natural disasters, catastrophic events and payments to areas facing natural or other constraints) are intended to restore pre-existing conditions and to ensure the maintenance of activities in disadvantaged areas. Such measures enjoy a relatively large amount of funds: about 60 millions Euro (Lazio RDP, measures 13 and 15)
3a. To what extent is the development of buffer resources enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	3	Both CMO and RDP objectives are heavily affected by the concern to promote a sustainable use of agricultural natural resources and mitigate the climate change. But no explicit role in the current policy objectives for financial buffer or compensation.

<p>3b. To what extent is the development of buffer resources enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>Operational Plans (OP) may fund crisis prevention and management, but a financial ceiling (33% of the OP) may constrain this buffer resource. Minimum threshold of financial resources in the POs' operational plans is required by the fruit and legume national strategy for the environmental actions. Further, a significant share of resources in the regional RDP is allocated to agro-environmental measures. RDP aids to restore agricultural production potential damaged by natural disasters and catastrophic events also contribute to buffer resources development.</p>
<p>4a. To what extent are other modes of managing risks enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>Both CMO and RDP objectives place great emphasis on risk management considering that “ The production of fruit and legumes is unpredictable ...Even limited surpluses can significantly disturb the market. Therefore, measures for crisis management should be establishedinto operational programmes. [REG. 1308/2013 – Considerando 37 - page 674]</p>
<p>4b. To what extent are other modes of managing risks enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>Only the measure regarding insurances has been implemented of the whole risk management package provided by the RDP. Measures regarding mutual funds in the operational programs and the Income Stabilization Tool, while approved, have not been implemented yet.</p>
<p>ADAPTABILITY</p>		
<p>1a. To what extent is a focus on the middle-long term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>Both CMO and RDP objectives are focused on medium and long term organizational and structural adjustments</p>
<p>1b. To what extent is a focus on the middle-long term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>Almost all the instruments used by CMO and RDP exert their action in the medium and long term</p>
<p>2a. To what extent is flexibility enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Horizontal and vertical coordination of the supply chain (promoted by CMO for fruit and legumes) may favor flexibility mainly at supply chain level according to change of market conditions over time.</p>

<p>2b. To what extent is flexibility enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>The instruments provided by CMO for fruit and legumes essentially promote flexibility for the whole supply chain and offer the opportunity to diversify the agricultural market outlets. Instruments supporting cooperation, joint supply and marketing actions are privileged. This allows diversification of marketing channels and adaptation to changing market conditions over time. But mandatory requirement for associated farmers to market their output through their PO.might slightly constrain flexibility.</p>
<p>3a. To what extent are variety and tailor-made responses enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>Individual and associated farmers may formulate their development programs by choosing only certain goals within a very broad set of objectives.</p>
<p>3b. To what extent are variety and tailor-made responses enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Although CMO offer extensive degrees of freedom in drawing the Producer Organizations' operational programs, there are some constraints to tailor-made responses. For example: the minimum financial threshold (10%) for environmental actions; the maximum financial ceiling (33%) for crisis prevention and management measures; mandatory requirement for associated farmers to market their output through their PO.</p>
<p>4a. To what extent is social learning enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>Strong emphasis on the objectives of enhancing networks of and cooperation among different operators.</p>
<p>4b. To what extent is social learning enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>The only networks effectively and explicitly supported by the RDP at regional level are the Operational Groups promoted by the European Innovation Partnership (EIP). Social learning is also fostered by cooperation measures within the CMO operational programs. But the dialogue is essentially restricted within the stakeholders involved in the supply chain and the financial resources for these networks are limited.</p>

TRANSFORMABILITY		
1a. To what extent is a focus on the long term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	2	A very long term vision and strategy is not explicitly present in the policy documents but some reference to young farmers program.
1b. To what extent is a focus on the long term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	3	Instruments supporting long term investments, innovation transfer and young farmers start-up focus on long term adjustments and transformations.
2a. To what extent is the dismantling of incentives that support the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	3	There is a significant focus on the objective of generational change in agriculture in the RDP. Given the greater propensity of young people to introduce technological and organizational innovations, generational change may contribute indirectly to dismantle the status quo activities and promote heavy change of processes and products.
2b. To what extent is the dismantling of incentives that support the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	2	At regional level RDP support, though with a substantial financial allocation, ONLY the starting up of entrepreneurial activities for young farmers.
3a. To what extent is in-depth learning enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	3	The RDP objectives concerning EIP emphasize the dialogue between farmers and the research community. The participation of all stakeholders in the knowledge exchange process is also encouraged.
3b. To what extent is in-depth learning enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	2	At regional level RDP provides only a very slight support for the establishment of EIP operational groups and the implementation of practical activities carried out in companies and research centers.
4a. To what extent is the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	4	According to the EIP programme, RDP at european and regional level place a strong emphasis on the transfer of knowledge and innovations in rural areas

<p>4b. To what extent is the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>The Regional Rural Development Plan supports pilot projects and the development of new products, techniques and production processes. However, the financial allocation is not appropriate to the ambition of the objectives.</p>
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3.2 – The ResAT wheels

Concerning the analysis and the scoring adopted in the previous paragraph, we need few premises. Firstly, both the policies affecting our CS farming systems (RD and CMO) are very complex and tend to crosswise affect most of the resilience dimensions and characteristics. As a consequence in our analysis, each objective and instrument examined has been attributed to the dimension/characteristics of resilience on which it is expected to exert a relatively greater impact. Secondly, particularly with respect to the policies analyzed (RD and CMO), it is quite seldom that a policy goal and instrument is explicitly addressed to counteract or constrain some kind of resilience dimension or characteristic. More generally, most of the goals and the instruments privilege a type of resilience rather than on another. For these reasons the assigned scores must be interpreted in a relative way. A score of 1 or 2 does not necessarily mean that such a policy constraints a certain trait of resilience, but rather that its expected impact on that trait is weaker or very weaker in comparison with alternative traits.

According to the results presented in table 1 we developed the following ResAT Wheels (fig. 1a and Fig. 1b). The first wheel concerns policy objectives and provides a comprehensive analysis of the policy makers’ willingness to constrain, enable or promote the different types the resilience of our farming systems. The second wheel concerns instruments and it provides an overview according to the policies’ expected outcome.

Fig. 1a - ResAT wheel: Objectives

Fig. 1b - ResAT wheel: Instruments

Both wheels show up a general policy orientation to enhance farming systems' adaptability though maintaining a significant concern for robustness in the short-run.

This statement is motivated by two factors. First, the main policies affecting the farming systems in our case study region are designed within a medium term financial framework (EU Multiannual Financial Framework). Second, such farming systems are mostly specialized in perennial crops (hazelnut farms) that involve high sunk costs in the phase of planting. This doesn't allow such farming systems to pursue transformability strategies in a reasonable time horizon.

In general, the resilience enabling characteristic appears more pronounced in the policy objectives rather than in the policy instruments. In most of the cases, it depends on the financial allocation to some instruments that doesn't seem adequate with respect to very ambitious objectives. The case of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) is particularly significant with this respect. The program's goals are very ambitious and aimed at: a) stimulating social and in depth learning through networks involving many stakeholders, including public and private research institutions;

b) fostering operational innovation through transfer of scientific knowledge and research results. But at the opposite, in the regional RDP the financial allocation to EIP program is very limited (only 1,5% of the whole RDP budget).

In some other cases, it depends on the constraints faced by the beneficiaries in order to get the financial support. In this latter case, such constraints limit the flexibility of farmers and POs to design tailor-made plans. In particular RDPs, even if they have greater financial support than Operational Plans within CMO, usually are not exploited enough by the farmers. That is because of the political and administrative burden occurring both in the implementation of the RD policy at regional level and in the complexity of the procedures and documents required to the potential beneficiaries. This is the case, for example of the policies promoting risk management practices where, in the face of a very broad package of measures provided by RD, only the access to insurance programs has been implemented and financed.

Finally, it should be emphasized that the wheels presented in Fig. 1 provide a general overview of policies whose objectives and instruments are quite different. In particular, according to the analysis presented in the annex (Tab. A1), CMO policy is strictly concerned with adaptability while RDP objectives and its instruments partly address also robustness and transformability concerns.

4 – Stakeholder check

The stakeholder check has been organized through four selected interviews. People interviewed are: the director of a POs Union (Italia Ortofrutta), the president of a PO specialized in hazelnut (Assofrutti), a technician (agronomist) working in the CS area and a farmer cropping around 80 hectares of hazelnut (table 2).

Table 2 – People interviewed

Name	Affiliation/Role	Contact	Date	Location
Vincenzo Falconi	Director Italia Ortofrutta	direzione@italiaortofrutta.it	Sept. 5, 2018	Italia Ortofrutta Head Office - Rome
Pompeo Mascagna	President Assofrutti	valentini Benedetto@libero.it	July 23, 2018	Assofrutti Head Office - Caprarola
Benedetto Valentini	Agronomist ARSIAL	pompeo@assofrutti.com	May 16, 2018	ARSIAL Local office - Ronciglione
Giorgio Monfeli	Hazelnut Farmer	monfeligiorgio@outlook.it	Sept. 6, 2018	Unitus, DEIM - Viterbo

The interviews were conducted with the following procedure:

- a) presentation of the project and its goals,
- b) explanation of the aim of the policy analysis,
- c) short definition of the resilience dimensions and characteristics,
- d) presentation of the colored ResAT wheels,
- e) discussion following a semi-structured questionnaire (Table A2 in the annex).

The results of the stakeholder check substantially confirmed our assessment and brought about some minor adjustment of the scores in table 2. All the persons interviewed emphasized the greater use and effectiveness of the measures provided by CMO because of their easy access and payments promptness. They agreed about the prevailing adaptive focus of the examined policies, especially with respect to CMO provisions. They also provided useful qualitative insights and suggestions concerning the actual effects of the adopted policies and their strengths and weakness. Their contributions have been heavily included in the arguments of table 1, in the interpretation of the ResAT wheels and in the conclusions of this report.

5 – Conclusions: overall analysis of policies' strengths and weaknesses

Given the characteristics and the specialization (hazelnut crops) of the farming systems prevailing in the area of this case study, the main policies examined in this document have been the Rural Development policy and the Common Market Organization for fruit and legumes.

The general picture coming out from our analysis points out that such policies address mainly the farming systems adaptation to external factors with some concern for the survival of the activity in the short run. Short run and status quo protection goals arise mainly with respect to occasional catastrophic/natural events and market crises. Only RD partly address farming systems transformability, in particular through the program for young farmers and the European Innovation Partnership for agriculture (EIP-Agri).

According to the five challenges affecting farming systems in our case study we refer to the following table that classify and qualify the characteristics of the intervention.

Rural development policies include many programs embracing several goals and instruments. In table 1 we show only the main programs directly addressing the challenges facing the CS farming systems. The strength points of the RDP for Lazio region include the large financial allocation for some measures and the opportunity to choose, within a wide range of measures, those that best meet the farming system need. On the other hand the main weaknesses of the RDP are the long and twisted path necessary to access the measures and the substantial delay in payments to the beneficiaries. The complexity of the administrative steps to implement the RDP often privilege the formal and documental fairness of the procedures but not the effective achievement of the goals of the program. It is the case, for example, of the young farmers program that, instead of promoting new young entrants in the business, induce surreptitious property changes within the same family, often with the unintentional effect to cause a further fragmentation of the farms.

Table 3 - Main policies addressing resilience to challenges facing the CS farming systems

	Socio - demographic	Political factors	Consumers preferences	Market Instability	Environmental factors
Policies	Young farmers program (RDP)	Agri-food policies do not fit this challenge but look at its major implication (market instability)	Supply chain coordination and POs' operational programs (CMO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk management package (RDP) • Crisis Prevention and Mgmt (CMO) • Supply chain coordination(CMO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catastrophic events and disadvantaged areas (RDP) • Environmental actions (CMO) and program (RDP) • EIP-Agri program(RDP)
Resilience dimension	Trasformability		Adaptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robustness (RDP) • Adaptability(CMO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robustness (RDP) • Adaptability (CMO-RDP) • Transformability (RDP)
Resilience characters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dismantling status quo • Innovation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexibility • Variety • Social learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk management • Flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buffer resources • Variety • Innovation/in-depth learning
Strenght	Great emphasis on the goal and large financial allocation		Tailor made operational programs fit farming systems needs to improve quality and quantity according to cons. preferences	Easy and prompt access to the measures adopted by POs operational programs.	Strong focus on environmental tailor made actions in policy goals and instruments. EIP-Agri programs might strenghten and widen further the technological frontier for this kind of actions.
Weakness	Only starting up actions and implementation problems (actually few new entrants and many opportunist property changes in order to get this financial support)		Weak instruments to achieve an enough degree of consolidation. Too fragmented POs are not able to carry out system actions effectively facing with changes of consumers preferences	Weak instruments and rules in CMO to promote an enough degree of POs consolidation. Too fragmented POs are not able to carry out an effective management of market risks. Implementation problems for RDP risk package (actually it rests only on support to insurance programs)	To many measures in too many programs without a clear demarcation of the boundaries between one measure/program and another. Risks of overlapping financial support and weak finalization and coordination of the actions. Poor financial sources for EIP-Agri program.

The other policy with high impact on the CS farming systems is the CMO for Fruit and Legumes. Because of the implementation problems characterizing the RDP, many farmers prefer to get the opportunities provided by the POs operational programs within the CMO despite their lower financial endowment. The strength points of the CMO include: the flexibility of the operational programs and the opportunity to tailor them according to the effective POs' goals and challenges; the easy and prompt farmers' access to their measures; the potential capability to promote the supply chain coordination and the farmers bargaining power; the strict link between the financial support of the operational program and the actual size of the PO business². Such characteristics allow the POs to increase their adaptive resilience in face of the challenges brought about by the

² The financial endowment of the operational program cannot exceed 2% of the PO actual marketed production.

changes of consumers preferences and the market instability. The main weakness of CMO is still the poor capability to induce a degree of POs consolidation able to face effectively with the challenges affecting the whole system such as market instabilities and crises. POs are still very fragmented to carry out system actions and their support is usually limited to improve farms' instrumental endowment and foster their development. Policy incentives and rules are not enough to counteract individualistic behaviors often induced by local political pressures and interests.

Though CMO provisions foster farming systems development and contribute to support adaptive resilience, their effectiveness in achieving the overall goals of the policy is still partial. That is because of the POs fragmentation but also because of the weak ability of the policy to address incentives toward the final objectives. At this purpose an interesting suggestion came out from the interviews to stakeholders. This is the possibility of linking the share of public co-financing of the POs' operational programs to the strategic impact of their actions and the value of the public good produced. It would be a sustainable and effective policy option to propose in the current discussion on the CAP reform.

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ANNEX

Table A1 – Analysis of policy documents

(REG.) Reg. 1308/2013 – National Strategy for Fruits and Legumes (N.S.F.L)

CMO for fruit and legumes			
Type of resilience	Key characteristics	Relevant texts for policy goals [add page number]	Relevant texts for policy instruments [add page number]
Robustness	1. Short term	None	None
	2. Protecting the status quo	<p>[N.d.R: obiettivi della misura 2 - Miglioramento o mantenimento della qualità dei prodotti] mantenere o migliorare la qualità dei prodotti freschi e trasformati dei soci delle OP, nella fase di produzione, raccolta, stoccaggio, condizionamento e trasformazione, <i>[N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 69]</i></p> <p>a) preservare e monitorare la qualità sia in campo che durante le fasi successive di lavorazione, condizionamento, stoccaggio e trasformazione dei prodotti; <i>[N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 70]</i></p>	<p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 2 - Miglioramento o mantenimento della qualità dei prodotti]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assistenza tecnica per mantenere ed elevare il livello di qualità dei prodotti; <i>[N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 71]</i>
	3. Buffer resources	<p>[N.d.R: finalità organizzazioni dei produttori] (viii) contributing to a sustainable use of natural resources and to climate change mitigation; <i>[REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 152 - page 738]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: finalità delle organizzazioni dei produttori] (iii) optimising production costs and returns on investments in response to environmental and animal welfare standards, and stabilising producer prices; <i>[REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 152 - page 737]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: finalità delle organizzazioni dei produttori] (v) promoting, and providing technical assistance for, the use of environmentally sound cultivation practices and production techniques, and sound animal welfare practices and techniques; <i>[REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 152 - page 738]</i></p>	<p>➤ Azioni ambientali Le OP/AOP possono inserire le azioni ambientali, inclusa l'agricoltura biologica e la produzione integrata, nei propri programmi operativi <i>[N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 59]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 1 - Pianificazione della produzione]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • realizzazione di impianti colturali aventi carattere pluriennale; • acquisto di macchine ed attrezzature per la semina/trapianto, raccolta e altre operazioni colturali specifiche per le colture ortofrutticole; <i>[N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 68]</i> <p>[N.d.R: dettagli inerenti le spese per il personale]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assistenza tecnica per migliorare o mantenere un elevato livello di protezione dell'ambiente <i>[N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 36]</i>
	4. Other risk management measures	<p>[N.d.R: cofinanziamento dei programmi operativi da parte dell'Ue]</p>	<p>[N.d.R: cofinanziamento Ue delle azioni dei programmi operativi] tutte le azioni che possono concorrere alle finalità perseguite dalle organizzazioni di</p>

		<p>(40) In order to give producer organisations and their associations in the fruit and legumes sector greater responsibility for their financial decisions and to direct the public resources assigned to them towards future requirements, terms should be set out for the use of those resources. Joint financing of operational funds set up by producer organisations and their associations is an appropriate solution. [REG. 1308/2013 – considerando 40 - page 674]</p> <p>(37) The production of fruit and legumes is unpredictable and the products are perishable. Even limited surpluses can significantly disturb the market. Therefore, measures for crisis management should be established and those measures should continue to be integrated into operational programmes. [REG. 1308/2013 – Considerando 37 - page 674]</p>	<p>produttori e quindi allo sviluppo dell'intero comparto ortofrutticolo nazionale, sono potenzialmente ammissibili nei programmi operativi e quindi al sostegno finanziario dell'Unione. [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 64]</p> <p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 6 - Prevenzione e gestione delle crisi]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • investimenti che rendano più efficace la gestione dei volumi immessi sul mercato. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. promozione e comunicazione, a titolo di prevenzione o durante il periodo di crisi; 2. ritiri dal mercato; 3. assicurazione del raccolto. <p>[N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 79]</p>
Adaptability	1. Middle-long term	<p>....</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Operational programmes in the fruit and legumes sector shall have a minimum duration of three years and a maximum duration of five years. [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 701] <p>[N.d.R: caratteristiche delle azioni da attivare]</p> <p>dotare le OP di proprie strutture di lavorazione e commercializzazione [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 65]</p>	<p>[N.d.R: Misura 7 - Azioni ambientali]</p> <p>Il sistema di qualità nazionale per la produzione integrata (SQNPI) è uno strumento fondamentale per la valorizzazione delle produzioni ottenute attraverso il metodo della produzione integrata [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 81]</p> <p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 3.1 incremento del valore commerciale dei prodotti e della commercializzazione]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • acquisto, costruzione o miglioramento e/o allestimento punti vendita dell'OP; • acquisto di terreni non edificati per la costruzione di magazzini di condizionamento, stoccaggio, lavorazione e trasformazione, piattaforme logistiche e punti di vendita dell'OP; <p>N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 72]</p>
	2. Flexibility	<p>[N.d.R: Programmi operativi]</p> <p>They shall have at least two of the objectives referred to in point (c) of Article 152(1) or two of the following objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (a) planning of production, including production and consumption forecasting and follow-up; (b) improvement of product quality, whether in a fresh or processed form; (c) boosting products' commercial value; (d) promotion of the products, whether in a fresh or processed form; (e) environmental measures, particularly those relating to water, and methods of 	<p>[N.d.R: Gli Stati membri garantiscono]</p> <p>(b) at least 10 % of the expenditure under operational programmes covers environmental actions. [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 702]</p> <p>(constraint)</p> <p>[N.d.R: condizioni per misure di prevenzione e gestione delle crisi]</p> <p>Crisis prevention and management measures, including any repayment of capital and interest as referred to in the fifth subparagraph, shall not comprise more than</p>

		<p>production respecting the environment, including organic farming; (f) crisis prevention and management. [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 701]</p> <p>[N.d.R: caratteristiche delle azioni da attivare] dotare le OP di proprio personale per gestire direttamente le fasi della programmazione, dell’assistenza tecnica e della commercializzazione, [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 65]</p>	<p>one third of the expenditure under the operational programme. [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 701] (constraint)</p> <p>[N.d.R: statuto organizzazioni di produttori del settore ortofrutticolo] The statutes of a producer organisation in the fruit and legumes sector shall require its producer members to market their entire production concerned through the producer organisation. [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 160 - page 742] (constraint)</p>
3. Variety and tailor-made responses		<p>[N.d.R: finalità delle organizzazioni dei produttori] (i) ensuring that production is planned and adjusted to demand, particularly in terms of quality and quantity; [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 152 - page 737]</p> <p>[N.d.R: obiettivi programmi operativi] 1. Operational programmes shall have at least two of the objectives referred to in point (c) of Article 152(1) or two of the following objectives: [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 701]</p> <p>[N.d.R: condizioni di ammissibilità investimenti per la pianificazione della produzione] 6) Le macchine e attrezzature agricole devono avere carattere innovativo tale da apportare miglioramenti tecnici all’interno di processi produttivi esistenti. [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 69]</p> <p>[N.d.R: obiettivi programmi operativi] (b) improvement of product quality, whether in a fresh or processed form; [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - pagina 701]</p> <p>[N.d.R: finalità delle organizzazioni dei produttori] vi) promuovere e fornire assistenza tecnica per il ricorso agli standard di produzione, per il miglioramento della qualità dei prodotti e lo sviluppo di prodotti con denominazione d'origine protetta, indicazione geografica protetta o coperti da un'etichetta di qualità nazionale; [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 152 - page 738]</p> <p>3. Crisis prevention and management referred to in point (f) of the first subparagraph of paragraph 1 shall be related to avoiding and dealing with crises</p>	<p>N.d.R: obiettivi programmi operativi] (a) planning of production, including production and consumption forecasting and follow-up; [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 701]</p> <p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 1 - Pianificazione della produzione] • acquisto di hardware per la gestione della base sociale, delle superfici e per il monitoraggio della produzione e dei conferimenti [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 68]</p> <p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 3.1 incremento del valore commerciale dei prodotti e della commercializzazione] • Assistenza tecnica per il miglioramento delle condizioni di commercializzazione; [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 73]</p> <p>[N.d.R: Misura 7 - Azioni ambientali] i programmi operativi definiscono quindi una specifica strategia volta ad assicurare la più ampia diffusione di tale sistema di qualità [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 81]</p> <p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 2 - Miglioramento o mantenimento della qualità dei prodotti] • acquisto di macchinari, attrezzature e apparecchiature per preservare e migliorare la qualità dei prodotti a partire dalla fase post-raccolta a quella di immissione sul mercato; [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 70]</p> <p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 2 - Miglioramento o mantenimento della qualità dei prodotti]</p>

		<p>on the fruit and vegetable markets and shall cover in this context: [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 701]</p> <p>(174) A special approach should be allowed in the case of farmers' or producer organisations or their associations, the objective of which is the joint production or marketing of agricultural products or the use of joint facilities.... [REG. 1308/2013 – Considerando 174 - page 687]</p> <p>[N.d.R: finalità delle organizzazioni dei produttori] (ii) concentration of supply and the placing on the market of the products produced by its members, including through direct marketing; (ix) developing initiatives in the area of promotion and marketing; [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 152 - page 737-738]</p> <p>[N.d.R: obiettivi misura 3 incremento del valore commerciale dei prodotti e della commercializzazione] favorire una migliore gestione commerciale del prodotto attraverso la disponibilità di strutture operative complete, dotate di impianti per il condizionamento, stoccaggio e trasformazione del prodotto, nonché di macchine e attrezzature e di contenitori (es: bins), per la gestione dei flussi di magazzino, monitorando nel contempo tutte le fasi della commercializzazione. [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 71]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spese specifiche per il miglioramento della qualità per mezzo dell'innovazione nella tecnica colturale delle piante arboree; [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 71] <p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 2 - Miglioramento o mantenimento della qualità dei prodotti] Servizi di consulenza per l'introduzione di sistemi certificati di qualità. [N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 71]</p> <p>[N.d.R: misure e interventi per la prevenzione e la gestione delle crisi] (a) investments making the management of the volumes placed on the market more efficient; (b) training measures and exchanges of best practices; (c) promotion and communication, whether for prevention or during a crisis period; (d) support for the administrative costs of setting up mutual funds; (e) replanting of orchards where that is necessary following mandatory grubbing up for health or phytosanitary reasons on the instruction of the Member State competent authority; (f) market withdrawal; (g) green harvesting or non-harvesting of fruit and legumes; (h) harvest insurance [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 701]</p> <p>Crisis prevention and management measures, including any repayment of capital and interest as referred to in the fifth subparagraph, shall not comprise more than one third of the expenditure under the operational programme. [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 701]</p> <p>Producer organisations may take out loans on commercial terms for financing crisis prevention and management measures. [REG. 1308/2013 – Art. 33 - page 701]</p> <p>[N.d.R: investimenti ammissibili misura 3.1 incremento del valore commerciale dei prodotti e della commercializzazione] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> acquisto di macchine, attrezzature e contenitori per la gestione dei flussi di magazzino; acquisto di accessori per allestire un mezzo al trasporto frigorifero o in atmosfera controllata; acquisto di hardware per il monitoraggio delle fasi di commercializzazione, anche ai fini della tracciabilità/rintracciabilità dei prodotti; acquisto di hardware per la gestione dei flussi di magazzino; acquisto di hardware per le vendite online; acquisto di software per le vendite online; </p>
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			<i>[N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 72-73]</i>
	4. Social learning	<p>[N.d.R: Effetti ambientali della produzione di ortofrutticoli] Tutto ciò ha comportato un crescente interesse dei consumatori per i prodotti di comprovata sostenibilità ambientale che rappresenta il migliore incentivo a perseguire nell'utilizzo e nello sviluppo delle tecniche di produzione rispettose dell'ambiente. <i>[N.S.F.L 2018-2022- attached to the DM n. 4969 del 29-08-2017- page 50]</i></p>	None
Transformability	1. Long term	None	None
	2. Dismantling incentives that support the status quo	None	None
	3. In-depth learning	None	None
	4. Enhancing and accelerating niche innovations	None	None

Rural Development Policy

Type of resilience	Key characteristics	Relevant texts for policy goals [add page number]	Relevant texts for policy instruments [add page number]
Robustness	1. Short term	None	None
	2. Protecting the status quo	<p>[N.d.R: Obiettivo misure di mitigazione, eventi catastrofici e calamità naturali] favorire la ripresa delle attività produttive attraverso il ripristino del potenziale produttivo agricolo e zootecnico danneggiato da calamità naturali o da eventi atmosferici <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 426]</i></p> <p>In order to help farm viability and competitiveness in the face of such disasters or events, support should be provided to help farmers restore agricultural potential which has been damaged. <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – considerando 16 - page 490]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: Obiettivo indennità a favore degli agricoltori delle zone montane o di altre zone soggette a vincoli naturali o ad altri vincoli specifici] encouraging continued use of agricultural land, contribute to maintaining and promoting sustainable farming systems. <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – considerando 25 - page 492]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: obiettivo Misura 13 - Indennità a favore delle zone soggette a vincoli naturali o ad altri vincoli specifici] “Promuovere la permanenza dell'attività agricola nelle zone soggette a vincoli naturali” <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 757]</i></p>	<p>[N.d.R: sostegno interventi per ripristino del potenziale produttivo agricolo danneggiato da calamità naturali e da eventi catastrofici] (b) investments for the restoration of agricultural land and production potential damaged by natural disasters, adverse climatic events and catastrophic events. <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 18 - page 507]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: costi ammissibili misura 5.2 - sostegno a investimenti per il ripristino dei terreni agricoli e del potenziale produttivo danneggiati da calamità naturali, avversità atmosferiche ed eventi catastrofici]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • il ripristino della capacità produttiva delle strutture aziendali • il ripristino di impianti arborei; • l’acquisto di animali in sostituzione di quelli che non possono più rientrare nel ciclo produttivo a seguito della calamità; • il ripristino di macchine e attrezzature in sostituzione di quelle danneggiate o distrutte dalla calamità naturale, • le spese generali. <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 427]</i> <p>[N.d.R: tipologia di aiuto, indennità a favore delle zone soggette a vincoli naturali o ad altri vincoli specifici] 1. Payments to farmers in mountain areas and other areas facing natural or other specific constraints shall be granted annually per hectare of agricultural area in order to compensate farmers for all or part of the additional costs and income foregone related to the constraints for agricultural production in the area concerned. <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 31- page 513]</i></p>
	3. Buffer resources	<p>[N.d.R: Obiettivo misure di mitigazione, eventi catastrofici e calamità naturali] favorire la ripresa delle attività produttive attraverso il ripristino del potenziale produttivo agricolo e zootecnico danneggiato da calamità naturali o da eventi atmosferici <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 426]</i></p>	<p>[N.d.R: sostegno interventi per ripristino del potenziale produttivo agricolo danneggiato da calamità naturali e da eventi catastrofici] (b) investments for the restoration of agricultural land and production potential damaged by natural disasters, adverse climatic events and catastrophic events. <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 18 - page 507]</i></p>

		<p>In order to help farm viability and competitiveness in the face of such disasters or events, support should be provided to help farmers restore agricultural potential which has been damaged. [REG. 1305/2013 – considerando 16 - page 490]</p> <p>[N.d.R: Obiettivo indennità a favore degli agricoltori delle zone montane o di altre zone soggette a vincoli naturali o ad altri vincoli specifici] encouraging continued use of agricultural land, contribute to maintaining the countryside [REG. 1305/2013 – considerando 25 - page 492]</p> <p>[N.d.R: obiettivo Misura 13 - Indennità a favore delle zone soggette a vincoli naturali o ad altri vincoli specifici] fabbisogno di una gestione attiva (di un “presidio”) dei territori più sottoposti a rischi ambientali ed in particolare ai rischi di erosione del suolo, al dissesto idrogeologico ma anche e soprattutto alla perdita della biodiversità. [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 757]</p> <p>N.d.R: logica d'intervento e il contributo agli aspetti specifici e agli obiettivi trasversali della misura sulla cooperazione] Determinate operazioni all'interno della misura perseguono il raggiungimento degli obiettivi trasversali legati alla gestione sostenibile delle risorse naturali [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 795]</p>	<p>[N.d.R: costi ammissibili misura 5.2 - sostegno a investimenti per il ripristino dei terreni agricoli e del potenziale produttivo danneggiati da calamità naturali, avversità atmosferiche ed eventi catastrofici]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • il ripristino della capacità produttiva delle strutture aziendali <p>....</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • il ripristino di impianti arborei; • l'acquisto di animali in sostituzione di quelli che non possono più rientrare nel ciclo produttivo a seguito della calamità; • il ripristino di macchine e attrezzature in sostituzione di quelle danneggiate o distrutte dalla calamità naturale, <p>....</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • le spese generali. <p>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 427]</p> <p>[N.d.R: tipologia di aiuto, indennità a favore delle zone soggette a vincoli naturali o ad altri vincoli specifici]</p> <p>1. Payments to farmers in mountain areas and other areas facing natural or other specific constraints shall be granted annually per hectare of agricultural area in order to compensate farmers for all or part of the additional costs and income foregone related to the constraints for agricultural production in the area concerned. [REG. 1305/2013 – articolo 31- pagina 513]</p> <p>[N.d.R: aspetti riguardanti la cooperazione]</p> <p>(g) joint approaches to environmental projects and ongoing environmental practices;</p> <p>(h) horizontal and vertical co-operation among supply chain actors in the sustainable provision of biomass for use in food and energy production and industrial processes; [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 35- page 516]</p>
4. Other risk management measures		<p>[N.d.R: logica d'intervento e il contributo agli aspetti specifici e agli obiettivi trasversali della misura sulla cooperazione] La misura persegue l'obiettivo di promuovere l'offerta e l'uso di strumenti di gestione del rischio in agricoltura attraverso il supporto alla prosecuzione e allo sviluppo del sistema assicurativo agevolato (sottomisura 17.1) [RDPN National 2014/2020 – page 220]</p>	<p>N.d.R: Ambiti di sostegno della misura – gestione del rischio] (a) financial contributions to premiums for crop, animal and plant insurance against economic losses to farmers caused by adverse climatic events, animal or plant diseases, pest infestation, or an environmental incident; [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 36 - page 517]</p> <p>N.d.R: Misura assicurazione del raccolto, degli animali e delle piante]</p> <p>1. Support under point (a) of Article 36(1) shall only be granted for insurance contracts which cover for loss caused by an adverse climatic event, or by an animal or plant disease, or a pest infestation, or an environmental incident [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 37 - page 518]</p> <p>N.d.R: Misura assicurazione del raccolto, degli animali e delle piante]</p>

			<p>Le operazioni cofinanziate si realizzano attraverso l'erogazione di un contributo pubblico che copre i costi finanziari sostenuti dagli imprenditori agricoli per il pagamento dei premi di assicurazione</p> <p><i>[RDPN National 2014/2020 – page 220]</i></p>
Adaptability	1. Middle-long term	<p>[N.d.R: durata del sostegno alla cooperazione di filiera] Such support should be limited to a period of seven years except for collective environmental and climate action in duly justified cases. <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – considerando 29 - page 493]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: durata dell'impegno agricoltura biologica] 3. Commitments under this measure shall be made for a period of five to seven years. <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 29 - page 512]</i></p>	None
	2. Flexibility	<p>[N.d.R: Combinazione e giustificazione delle misure di sviluppo rurale misura 1 (Trasferimento di conoscenze e azioni di informazione) e 16 (cooperazione)] rinsaldare i nessi tra agricoltura, produzione alimentare e silvicoltura <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 179]</i></p>	16.5 supporto per le azioni congiunte finalizzate all'adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 796]</i>
	3. Variety and tailor-made responses	<p>[N.d.R: Combinazione e giustificazione delle misure di sviluppo rurale misura 1 (Trasferimento di conoscenze e azioni di informazione) e 16 (cooperazione)] rinsaldare i nessi tra agricoltura, produzione alimentare e silvicoltura <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 179]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: logica d'intervento e il contributo agli aspetti specifici e agli obiettivi trasversali della misura sulla cooperazione] Determinate operazioni all'interno della misura perseguono il raggiungimento degli obiettivi trasversali legati all'azione per il clima. <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 795]</i></p> <p>(4) To ensure the sustainable development of rural areas, it is necessary to focus on a limited number of core priorities relating to knowledge transfer and innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas, to farm viability, to the competitiveness of all types of agriculture in all regions <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – considerando 4 - page 487]</i></p>	<p>[N.d.R: interventi previsti nella Misura 16 - cooperazione] 16.3 cooperazione tra piccoli operatori nell'organizzazione di processi di lavoro comuni e la condivisione di strutture e risorse, e per lo sviluppo e il marketing turistico; 16.4 sostegno alla cooperazione orizzontale e verticale tra gli attori della catena di approvvigionamento per la creazione e lo sviluppo di filiere corte e mercati locali e per le attività di promozione in un contesto locale relativamente allo sviluppo di filiere corte e di mercati locali; <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 796]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: sostegno interventi per ripristino del potenziale produttivo agricolo danneggiato da calamità naturali e da eventi catastrofici] (a) investments in preventive actions aimed at reducing the consequences of probable natural disasters, adverse climatic events and catastrophic events;; <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 18 - page 507]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: Misure di mitigazione eventi catastrofici e calamità naturali] • 5.1 - sostegno a investimenti in azioni di prevenzione volte a ridurre le conseguenze di probabili calamità naturali, avversità atmosferiche ed eventi catastrofici <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 420]</i></p>

			<p>N.d.R: interventi previsti nella Misura 16 - cooperazione] 16.5 supporto per le azioni congiunte finalizzate alla mitigazione dei cambiamenti climatici... 16.10 sostegno per la cooperazione all'interno della Filiera Organizzata <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 796]</i></p> <p>.... (e) promotion activities in a local context relating to the development of short supply chains and local markets; (f) joint action undertaken with a view to mitigating or adapting to climate change; <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 35- page 516]</i></p>
4. Social learning		<p>[N.d.R: obiettivi misura sulla cooperazione] 1. Support under this measure shall be granted in order to promote forms of co-operation involving at least two entities and in particular: (a) co-operation approaches among different actors in the Union agriculture sector, forestry sector and food chain and other actors that contribute to achieving the objectives and priorities of rural development policy, including producer groups, cooperatives and inter-branch organisations; <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 35- page 516]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: Combinazione e giustificazione delle misure di sviluppo rurale misura 1 (Trasferimento di conoscenze e azioni di informazione) e 16 (cooperazione)] rinsaldare i nessi tra agricoltura, produzione alimentare e silvicoltura <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 179]</i></p> <p>N.d.R: logica d'intervento e il contributo agli aspetti specifici e agli obiettivi trasversali della misura sulla cooperazione] Determinate operazioni all'interno della misura perseguono il raggiungimento degli obiettivi trasversali legati alla gestione sostenibile delle risorse naturali <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 795]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: Trasferimento di conoscenze e azioni di informazione] The knowledge and information acquired should enable farmers, forest holders, persons engaged in the food sector and rural SMEs to, in particular, enhance their competitiveness and resource efficiency and improve their environmental</p>	<p>[N.d.R: Elenco indicativo di misure e interventi di particolare rilevanza per il sottoprogramma tematico dei giovani agricoltori] Young farmers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer and information actions • Advisory services, farm management and farm relief services • Co-operation <i>[REG. 1305/2013 –allegato IV- page 543]</i></p> <p>(f) joint action undertaken with a view to mitigating or adapting to climate change; <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 35- page 516]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: interventi previsti nella Misura 16 - cooperazione] 16.3 cooperazione tra piccoli operatori nell'organizzazione di processi di lavoro comuni e la condivisione di strutture e risorse, e per lo sviluppo e il marketing turistico; 16.4 sostegno alla cooperazione orizzontale e verticale tra gli attori della catena di approvvigionamento per la creazione e lo sviluppo di filiere corte e mercati locali e per le attività di promozione in un contesto locale relativamente allo sviluppo di filiere corte e di mercati locali; <i>[RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 796]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: aspetti riguardanti la cooperazione] (g) joint approaches to environmental projects and ongoing environmental practices; (h) horizontal and vertical co-operation among supply chain actors in the sustainable provision of biomass for use in food and energy production and industrial processes; <i>[REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 35- page 516]</i></p> <p>[N.d.R: misura - trasferimento di conoscenze e azioni di informazione]</p>

		<p>performance while at the same time contributing to the sustainability of the rural economy. [REG. 1305/2013 – considerando 12 - pages 488 - 489]</p> <p>[N.d.R: Finalità della rete PEI] (b) establish a dialogue between farmers and the research community and facilitate the inclusion of all stakeholders in the knowledge exchange process. [REG. 1305/2013 – Articolo 53 - page 524]</p> <p>1. Support under this measure shall be granted in order to promote forms of co-operation involving at least two entities and in particular: (b) the creation of clusters and networks; [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 35- page 516]</p>	<p>1. Support under this measure shall cover vocational training and skills acquisition actions, demonstration activities and information actions. [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 14 - page 504]</p>
<p>Transfor mability</p>	<p>1. Long term</p>	<p>[N.d.R: obiettivo sviluppo delle aree rurali] (17) For the development of rural areas, the creation and development of new economic activity in the form of new farms, A farm and business development measure should facilitate the initial establishment of young farmers and the structural adjustment of their agricultural holding after the initial setting up. [REG. 1305/2013 – considerando 17 - page 490]</p>	<p>[N.d.R: interventi sostenuti nel quadro di sottoprogrammi tematici]</p> <p>In the case of young farmers and mountain areas, the maximum support rates may be increased in accordance with Annex II. However, the maximum combined support rate shall not exceed 90 %. [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 7- page 501]</p> <p>[N.d.R: misura relativa allo sviluppo delle aziende agricole e delle imprese] 1. Support under this measure shall cover: (a) business start-up aid for: (i) young farmers; [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 19- page 507]</p> <p>[N.d.R: misura 6.1 - aiuti all'avviamento di imprese per i giovani agricoltori] Il premio concesso per l'insediamento è di 70.000 euro ed è limitato alle micro e piccole imprese [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 439]</p> <p>[N.d.R: Elenco indicativo di misure e interventi di particolare rilevanza per il sottoprogramma tematico dei giovani agricoltori] Young farmers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business start-up aid for young farmers setting up for the first time in an agricultural holding [REG. 1305/2013 –allegato IV- page 543]</p>
	<p>2. Dismantling incentives that support the status quo</p>	<p>[N.d.R: obiettivo sviluppo delle aree rurali] (17) For the development of rural areas, the creation and development of new economic activity in the form of new farms, A farm and business development measure</p>	<p>[N.d.R: interventi sostenuti nel quadro di sottoprogrammi tematici]</p> <p>In the case of young farmers and mountain areas, the maximum support rates may be increased in accordance with Annex II. However, the</p>

		<p>should facilitate the initial establishment of young farmers and the structural adjustment of their agricultural holding after the initial setting up. [REG. 1305/2013 – considerando 17 - page 490]</p> <p>Il contributo del PSR all’obiettivo di favorire l’ingresso di agricoltori adeguatamente qualificati nel settore agricolo e, in particolare, il ricambio generazionale (Focus 2B) è perseguito principalmente attraverso l’operazione 6.1.1 aiuti all’avviamento aziendale per giovani agricoltori. [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 182]</p>	<p>maximum combined support rate shall not exceed 90 %. [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 7- page 501]</p> <p>[N.d.R: misura relativa allo sviluppo delle aziende agricole e delle imprese] 1. Support under this measure shall cover: (a) business start-up aid for: (i) young farmers; [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 19- page 507]</p> <p>[N.d.R: Elenco indicativo di misure e interventi di particolare rilevanza per il sottoprogramma tematico dei giovani agricoltori] Young farmers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business start-up aid for young farmers setting up for the first time in an agricultural holding • Investments in physical assets • Advisory services, farm management and farm relief services • Investments in non-agricultural activities <p>[REG. 1305/2013 –allegato IV- page 543]</p> <p>[N.d.R: misura 6.1 - aiuti all'avviamento di imprese per i giovani agricoltori] Il premio concesso per l’insediamento è di 70.000 euro ed è limitato alle micro e piccole imprese [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 439]</p>
3. In-depth learning		<p>[N.d.R: obiettivo misura sulla cooperazione] (c) the establishment and operation of operational groups of the EIP for agricultural productivity and sustainability [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 35- page 516]</p> <p>N.d.R: istituzione e finalità della rete del partenariato europeo per l'innovazione] 1. A EIP network shall be put in place to support the EIP for agricultural productivity and sustainability referred to in Article 55, in accordance with Article 51(1). It shall enable the networking of operational groups, advisory services and researchers 2. The aim of the EIP network shall be to: (a) facilitate the exchange of expertise and good practices; (b) establish a dialogue between farmers and the research community and facilitate the inclusion of all stakeholders in the knowledge exchange process. [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 53- page 524]</p>	<p>[N.d.R: misura - trasferimento di conoscenze e azioni di informazione] 1. Support under this measure shall cover vocational training and skills acquisition actions, demonstration activities and information actions. [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 14 - page 504]</p> <p>[N.d.R: Operazione 1.2.1 – sostegno ad attività dimostrative e azioni di informazione] L’operazione 1.2.1 sostiene sia la realizzazione di attività pratiche svolte presso aziende e centri di ricerca sia attività informative capillari rivolte a tutti gli operatori delle aree rurali. [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 179]</p> <p>[N.d.R: Combinazione e giustificazione delle misure di sviluppo rurale misura 1 (Trasferimento di conoscenze e azioni di informazione) e 16 (cooperazione)] Le operazioni attivate dalla Regione sono legate al funzionamento dei Gruppi Operativi (16.1.1) [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 179]</p>
4. Enhancing and accelerating niche		<p>[N.d.R: Priorità dell'Unione in materia di sviluppo rurale]</p>	<p>[N.d.R: Operazione 1.1.1 - sostegno ad azioni di formazione professionale e acquisizione di competenze]</p>

	<p>innovations</p>	<p>(1) fostering knowledge transfer and innovation in agriculture, forestry, and rural areas with a focus on the following areas: (a) fostering innovation, cooperation, and the development of the knowledge base in rural areas; (b) strengthening the links between agriculture, food production and forestry and research and innovation, including for the purpose of improved environmental management and performance; [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 5 - page 500]</p> <p>[N.d.R: logica d'intervento e il contributo agli aspetti specifici e agli obiettivi trasversali della misura sulla cooperazione] Determinate operazioni all'interno della misura perseguono il raggiungimento degli obiettivi trasversali legati all'innovazione [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 795]</p> <p>[N.d.R: Combinazione e giustificazione delle misure di sviluppo rurale misura 1 (Trasferimento di conoscenze e azioni di informazione) e 16 (cooperazione)] Le operazioni concorrono direttamente all'obiettivo specifico di ricerca e innovazione,, anche al fine di migliorare la gestione e le prestazioni ambientali [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 179]</p>	<p>È finalizzata all'accrescimento delle competenze attraverso il sostegno ad attività formative finalizzate all'acquisizione delle adeguate conoscenze tecniche e professionali per migliorare la competitività e l'efficienza dell'impresa, la gestione sostenibile delle risorse naturali, l'utilizzo di tecniche e pratiche aziendali a minor impatto ambientale ed ecocompatibili, per ottimizzare i processi [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 179]</p> <p>[N.d.R: aspetti riguardanti la cooperazione] (a) pilot projects; (b) the development of new products, practices, processes and technologies in the agriculture, food and forestry sectors; [REG. 1305/2013 – Art. 35- page 516]</p> <p>[N.d.R: Combinazione e giustificazione delle misure di sviluppo rurale misura 1 (Trasferimento di conoscenze e azioni di informazione) e 16 (cooperazione)] Le operazioni attivate dalla Regione sono legate alla realizzazione dei progetti pilota previsti (16.2.1). [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 179]</p> <p>[N.d.R: interventi previsti nella Misura 16 - cooperazione] 16.2 sostegno a progetti pilota e per lo sviluppo di nuovi prodotti, pratiche, processi e tecnologie; [RDP Regional 2014/2020 – page 796]</p>
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Table A2 – Semi-structured questionnaire for stakeholders check

ROBUSTEZZA/RESISTENZA

1. In che misura e con quali strumenti la PAC favorisce o limita il mantenimento dello status quo (stessi prodotti, stessi processi produttivi, stesse strutture aziendali)? Sarebbero auspicabili interventi alternativi in questo senso?
2. In che misura e con quali strumenti la PAC favorisce o limita lo sviluppo di scorte di prodotti, inputs e risorse agrarie? Sarebbero auspicabili interventi alternativi in questo senso?
3. In che misura e con quali strumenti la PAC favorisce o limita la gestione del rischio rispetto ad avversità climatiche, patogene e, di mercato? Sarebbero auspicabili interventi alternativi in questo senso?

FLESSIBILITA'/ADATTABILITA'

4. In che misura e con quali strumenti la PAC favorisce o limita la flessibilità e/o l'adattamento dei processi produttivi e commerciali per fronteggiare l'incertezza ed il cambiamento delle condizioni produttive e di mercato? Sarebbero auspicabili interventi alternativi in questo senso?
5. In che misura e con quali strumenti la PAC favorisce o limita la varietà degli aggiustamenti e lo sviluppo di attività ed investimenti tagliati sulle specifiche condizioni aziendali? Sarebbero auspicabili interventi alternativi in questo senso?
6. In che misura e con quali strumenti la PAC favorisce o limita i processi di apprendimento tecnico-economico anche e soprattutto attraverso l'associazionismo, le reti ed i rapporti tra operatori con diverse attività nella filiera? Sarebbero auspicabili interventi alternativi in questo senso?

TRASFORMAZIONE RADICALE/INNOVATIVITA'

7. In che misura e con quali strumenti la PAC favorisce o limita lo smantellamento degli attuali processi e strutture aziendali e commerciali per favorire una radicale trasformazione dell'attività a fronte di strutturali cambiamenti delle condizioni produttive e commerciali? Sarebbero auspicabili interventi alternativi in questo senso?
8. In che misura e con quali strumenti la PAC favorisce o limita l'apprendimento di modelli produttivi innovativi e radicalmente diversi da quelli comunemente praticati anche e soprattutto con il coinvolgimento di soggetti ed istituzioni diverse (ricerca, industria, scuole e università ecc.) ? Sarebbero auspicabili interventi alternativi in questo senso?
9. In che misura e con quali strumenti la PAC favorisce o limita lo sviluppo e l'introduzione di innovazioni tecnologiche, organizzative e commerciali? Sarebbero auspicabili interventi alternativi in questo senso?